

NDC ASPECTS

Country Report

Transition pathways for Norway

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Stefan Kronshage
German Aerospace Center (DLR)
Institute of Networked Energy Systems

Pernille Seljom, PhD
Institute for Energy Technology (IFE)
Kjeller, Norway

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Key messages

- In the overall picture of the Norwegian climate protection ambition, the Climate Action Tracker indicated an overall rating as “almost sufficient” on Dec 2022.
- However, despite a long history and present mechanisms of Norwegian policy for climate protection, still considerably stronger policies and finance as well as effective implementation will be needed to meet the -55% NDC target for 2030 (Climate Action Tracker, 2022).
- For 2050, Norway has stated a 90-95% reduction target for its gross domestic greenhouse gas emissions (GHG), committing to become a “low emission society” in 2050. The GHG removals by LULUCF are expected to remain at the current considerable level of 15-20 MtCO₂e per year at a total current annual emission level of around 50 MtCO₂e. Thus, with a gross 90-95% emission reduction target, Norway will be a net GHG sink, including LULUCF (Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry).
- On the policy side, Norway demonstrates how a country can adopt and be part of European climate protection schemes like the EU-ETS without being an EU Member State. Other countries may adopt best-practices from the Norwegian case.
- Norway’s domestic GHG mitigation targets and efforts are counteracted by the Norwegian efforts to still expand its large oil and natural gas exploration and exporting sector (Climate Action Tracker, 2022). With the “EU energy crisis” from the Russian invasion in Ukraine in 2022 and, accordingly, Russian oil and gas supply being omitted as a crucial provider of the EU, the Norwegian oil and gas supplier Equinor ASA (former Statoil ASA) took over the role of the one predominant EU natural gas supplier.

Introduction and overview

Norway is a country with an extraordinary position in Europe regarding its starting point for sectoral defossilization and its strategic positioning as a key energy supplier for Europe. While many northern European countries and the EU27 have significantly reduced their greenhouse gas emissions since 1990, Norway has only recently, after 2015, gained first gross reductions compared to 1990 (NOU, 2023). However, on the one hand, Norway’s domestic supply system for electricity provision is already widely decarbonized based on large hydro-power capacities. On the other hand, Norway’s national economic activity is historically strongly depending on fossil oil and gas exploration and export. In the energy crisis from 2022 on, Norway went through a fundamental change regarding this position, making it in an even more extraordinary oil and gas exporter for European energy supply. The challenge for Norway is thus, on the one hand, directed toward further defossilizing its domestic demand sectors and managing the enormous necessary renewable electricity infrastructure expansion. Regarding electrification, Norway is a front-runner in the buildings sector (heat pumps) and in road passenger transport: Norway has the highest share of electric vehicles (EV) worldwide, both in its car fleet (22% in 2021) and car sales with an 85% share (IEA 2022, pure battery and plug-in hybrid). On the other hand, the challenge for the Norwegian government and fossil fuel industry will be how to handle the European fossil fuel phase-out economically and how to position itself on the political stage in the international climate change mitigation ambitions while defossilizing its domestic emitting sectors.

Key topics of the country

Key topics for Norway's climate action in the context of its NDC and long-term emission targets are:

- defossilizing Norway's industries and the yet fossil fuel-based parts of the transport system (see Figure 7 and Figure 12),
- covering the increasing demand of renewable electricity and grid capacities for the decarbonization of the key emitting sectors and for newly emerging industries (data centres, battery factories etc),
- establishing stronger climate policies in terms of more ambitious, broader and credible policy instruments, measures and political leadership (NOU, 2023),
- leading its extensive fossil fuel extraction and export activities with its large share of Norway's GDP into a Paris Agreement compatible energy future within the next 25 years.

Vastly reducing the industry GHG emissions and eliminating the remaining transport sector emissions is a key priority for Norway as the power sector is already mostly defossilised and agriculture and forestry already constitute major GHG sinks. Further information on the sector-specific defossilization options and pathways is explicated in the sectoral sections below.

The ambition of the Norwegian state on climate change mitigation is perceived as being counteracted by its ambition to still expand the yet extensive fossil fuel exploration and export activities. In 2021, a case was brought forward to the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) by two NGOs and affiliated individuals, complaining about unsuccessful juridical efforts to declare invalid a decision made by the Norwegian Government to grant petroleum exploration licenses for the Norwegian continental shelf. In 2023, the Court announced to adjourn this case until the Grand Chamber has decided on the other climate change cases before it (ECHR, 2023). Policy, however, is not made by the court, so it will be a prominent showcase in Europe how the Norwegian government will interpret and organize its dual role between its extensive fossil fuel industry and ambitious domestic GHG reduction emissions. In addition, Carbon Captures and Storage (CCS) is an important area for Norway's climate action. By its support schemes for CCS, Norway has currently gained a leading position in CCS expertise and experience, hosting several companies in the field of CCS (IEA, 2022). The prominent Langskip CCS plant project, with a planned CO₂ delivery of 800.000 tons per year, is in a progressed state of construction (GASSNOVA, 2024). And the Norwegian petroleum industry is investigating the production of blue hydrogen from Norwegian natural gas including capture and storage of the carbon dioxide emissions (Equinor, 2024). The role, however, that CCS will play in achieving the Norwegian long-term climate targets is not yet clearly visible.

Hydrogen as a molecule-based energy carrier with the connected technologies is expected to play an important role in the Norwegian energy system. The government and several industrial actors including Equinor have a strategy of Norway being a large producer of hydrogen, both blue (natural gas based with CCS, see Equinor 2024) and green (from renewables using electrolysis) and both for export and domestic use.

National targets (NDC) and programs/policies

On 3rd November 2022, the second updated revision of the first Norwegian NDC (Nationally Determined Contribution) has been submitted to the UNFCCC (NDC, 2022). Norway therein commits to a target of **at least 55% reduction of greenhouse gas emission compared to 1990 levels by 2030** excl. LULUCF. The NDC target achieved a legal status by being established in the Norwegian Climate Change Act in its updated version of June 2021. The Climate Action Tracker rated the Norwegian NDC target for 2030 against modelled domestic pathways positively as

“1.5°C Global Least Cost” on Dec 1st, 2022, corresponding to the minimum ambition in Norway for achieving a below 1.5°C world (Climate Action Tracker, 2022).

Norway has not introduced an explicit net zero target. By committing to a **90-95% GHG reduction by 2050** below 1990 levels (51.5 MtCO₂e/a in 1990) excluding LULUCF in its long-term strategy submitted to the UNFCCC in 2021, Norway has stated its national target as becoming a “**low emission society**” until 2050. When including the substantial Norwegian LULUCF sinks in the emissions accounting, a gross emission reduction by 90-95% compared to 1990 would clearly mean Norway being a net negative emission country, domestically. The Climate Action Tracker rates this target for 2050 as “average” (Climate Action Tracker, 2022).

According to the further specifications of the 2022 NDC, the main policy instruments for the implementation of the NDC target by 2030 are

- taxation of greenhouse gas emissions and regulatory measures like the emissions trading scheme according to EU ETS,
- climate-related requirements in public procurement processes,
- information on climate-friendly options,
- financial support for the development of new technologies, such as CCS, and
- initiatives to promote research and innovation in clean energy (NDC, 2022).

Norway states the climate cooperation with the EU as a key pillar for fulfilling its NDC target and for raising the ambition beyond the stated NDC. For example, Norway participates in the EU Emission Trading System for the industry and energy sector EU ETS 1 already since 2008 (NDC, 2022). However, On Norway’s participation in the now established EU-ETS 2 for the building and transport sector, no decisions have yet been made.

In Norway, the Ministry of Climate and Environment is responsible for the overarching cross-sectoral coordination and implementation of the national climate-change-related activities. For the tax schemes, the Norwegian Ministry of Finance is in charge.

In total, the Climate Action Tracker assessed the Norwegian policies and action as “almost sufficient” against modelled domestic pathways, corresponding to a 2°C world, at the end of 2022 while the climate-related finance is regarded as insufficient (Climate Action Tracker, 2022). Still considerably stronger policies and finance will be needed to meet the -55% NDC target for 2030 than established at the end of 2022, according to the Climate Action Tracker, and emissions from exported Norwegian oil and natural gas are not considered in this rating. The same conclusion applies for Norway’s target to become a “low emission society” by 2050, expressed in its 90-95% GHG emissions reduction target. The 2050 Climate Change Committee’s report (NOU 2023, see next chapter) quantifies the gap in 2050 between projected emissions excluding forestry and land use and the 95% target with around 17 MtCO₂e/a, which amounts to one third of the current emissions (Figure 1).

Key decarbonization pathways & related transformations

A prominent report being submitted in October 2023 is **The 2050 Climate Change Committee** report: “The transition to low emissions – Climate policy choices towards 2050” (Norwegian Official Report NOU 2023:25). Figure 1 shows its projections on GHG emissions until 2050, starting from historical emissions and also quantifying GHG sinks. It shows that projected gross emissions in total do not decline sufficiently to reach the low emission target of

-90 to 95 percent in 2050, leaving a gap of 15-17 MtCO₂e. Figure 2, in contrast, shows a target-oriented pathway of gross GHG emissions to 2050 resolved by the domestic sectors' contributions, with historical emissions in 1990 and 2021, a projection for 2030 and remaining 2050 emissions based on the technical analysis of the report (NOU, 2023). "Negative emissions" from the industry and energy sector are not included in the figure, resulting when including technological GHG removals here are accounted for in the balance in the sectors (see Table 2 and Figure 14). Emissions and removals from forestry and land use are not included in Figure 2, as well. From today's state on, all sectors show a steady decline of their emissions, including the petroleum extraction industry.

Figure 1: Historical GHG emissions and projections until 2050 including sinks (NOU, 2023)

Regarding the development of the energy carrier mix for a low emission 2050 energy system in Norway, the NOU 2023 report does not show a balance of the mix until 2050. But important messages of the report are: Biomass is a scarce and precious resource and its use should be prioritized for other purposes than energy use. Even then, biomass will play a role in the future Norwegian energy mix where decarbonization from electrification is difficult like in some transport segments (e.g. aviation, shipping) and in industrial applications (see Figure 3). Regarding nuclear energy, the report concludes that it currently is not a viable option for the Norwegian energy system but that the international development of new reactor types like small modular reactors (SMR) should be well observed. But nuclear as an energy option is highly discussed currently on the political stage, bringing up new initiatives into this directive.

Figure 2: Development of sectoral GHG emissions until 2050 (NOU, 2023)

The key pillar of a mainly decarbonized Norwegian energy system in 2050 is the accelerated electrification of end-uses based on a decarbonised power system with a large uptake of renewable energy sources beyond biomass to produce electricity. Solar power is discussed despite Norway's geographical location and climate conditions; solar PV can be installed on roofs, facades and ground-mounted indicating a still considerable technical potential. As Norway has very favourable wind conditions, onshore and offshore wind are expected to play a key role besides hydro power. Norway could benefit from its expertise from marine petroleum extraction for exploiting larger areas for floating wind offshore installations (NOU, 2023). The Statnett long-term market analysis report from 2023 for example (Norwegian Transmission System Operator, see below) describes the energy carrier pathway to 2050 in the same way as depicted in Figure 5.

Emissions from fossil oil and gas extraction by the Norwegian industry are substantial, thus it is of special importance how future pathways for petroleum extraction look like. Figure 4 shows different trajectories based on assumptions on fossil resource availability and technology development (NOU, 2023). While a decline to almost zero could be possible in the low scenario, the spectrum of up to around 125 scm oil equivalents is considerable, leaving a broad space of possible futures on this industry open.

Figure 3: Potential contributions of decarbonization measures to the 2050 target (NOU, 2023)

Figure 4: Oil and gas production scenarios to 2050 from the Norwegian Petroleum Directorate (NOU, 2023) (scm oe: standard cubic meters oil equivalents)

Beyond the NOU report of the Norwegian Climate Change Committee, long-term development studies are presented by institutional bodies like the Norwegian Transmission System Operator Statnett (2023) or the Norwegian Water and Energy Directorate (NVE, 2023). A recent research report on socio-technical pathways and scenario analysis to be mentioned is the 2023 report of the Norwegian Center for Energy Transition Strategies (NTRANS, 2023). In addition, various scenario data convolutes for Norway in the Sixth Assessment Report published in the AR6 Scenarios Database (IIASA) exist. From a commercial and company background there are scenarios which have a general transformation perspective and explicitly address sectoral transformation: the “Energy Transition Norway 2023” national forecast to 2050 by the international assurance and risk management provider DNV (2023) or “Norway’s path to Net Zero” as part of the Boston Consulting Group’s “Nordic Net Zero” project (BCG, 2022). The International Energy Agency recommended in its Norway 2022 report that the Norwegian government itself should set up own detailed pathways on the decarbonization of the sectors up to 2050 from detailed bottom-up technology modelling, stating in the same time a gap regarding these national scenarios (IEA, 2022).

Figure 5: Electricity supply until 2050, base scenario (Statnett 2023)

Sectoral system transformations

Achieving Norway’s stated 2030 NDC of -55% gross GHG reduction and the 2050 target of -90 to -95% requires concrete transformation in each of the sectors industry, transport, buildings and AFOLU (Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use) and the corresponding energy supply system. The Norwegian Governments long-term low-emission strategy for 2050 stated in 2020 explicitly requires that emissions are low in all sectors in 2050 (NOU, 2023). However, each sector has specific characteristics and properties that require dedicated decarbonization measures and strategies. Yet, one important common leverage for defossilizing the demand sectors in Norway, like the building sector and road passenger transport, is the low level of electricity prices that Norway has seen historically and still does so at present.

The following sector-specific chapters highlight specific focal aspects and characteristics of the Norwegian sectoral decarbonization pathways and strategies.

Industry

In the Norwegian industry sector, the petroleum industry plays a predominant and exceptional role. It generates around a fifth of Norway's GDP, and around half of the total national exports origin from this sector (Figure 6).

Source: National Accounts, National Budget 2023

Figure 6: Macroeconomic indicators for the petroleum sector* 2021 (National Communication 2023)

*Service and supply industry not included

Among the “mainland” industry branches, i.e. without oil and gas extraction and transport via pipelines and ocean transport, the aluminium industry has a strong position in Norway. For Norway's key industries, the following facts are to be mentioned for the industry sector's defossilization.

- Petroleum industry
 - Norway supplies around 30% of Europe's natural gas demand, of which two third origin from Equinor (Rocha, Lundgren, 2024). The Norwegian state owns around two third of Equinor shares.
 - The Norwegian Petroleum Directorate's has forecasted annual emissions of more than 500 Mt CO₂e for the years 2024 and 2025 from the combustion of oil and gas exploited by Norway (Figure 13, NOU 2023). This amounts to ten times the total domestic Norwegian emissions of greenhouse gases. To ensure economic growth and well-being at current levels, the GDP loss from turning away from oil and gas extraction and use for this main value adding industry branch has to be compensated for, and currently planned expansions of hydrogen and electricity production are not sufficient do so (DNV, 2023). More ambitious expansion plans of sources of national product in line with defossilization pathways would be favourable, not only to reach the mitigation targets, but also to maintain Norway's economic growth and create new jobs. Scenarios exist which indicate that decarbonisation of Norway's fossil oil and gas industry is possible while maintaining economic growth (BCG, 2022).
- Aluminium industry
 - The aluminium industry is strong in Norway with a production capacity of 1.3 Mt in 2023 and 1.4 Mt in 2022 (USGS, 2024).
 - If this capacity was completely shifted to electrified production, an additional electricity demand of 12.3 kWh/kg aluminium would be required (European Aluminium, 2019), leading to a total

- additional electricity demand of 17.2 TWh/a or more than 10 % of today's power consumption.
- Among the process-related emission reductions, the switch to emission-free inert anodes for aluminium alone has the potential do abate 3.3 MtCO₂e/a by 2050 (BCG, 2022)
- Other industrial products
 - Besides aluminium, and as generally seen in national industries, it is seen critical to immediately address the other "hard-to-abate" metals like ferroalloys as well as cement and chemicals production (BCG, 2022).
 - To substitute fossil reductants like coke in ferroalloys production, a substantial ramp-up of biocarbon reductants use needs to be induced, in the BCG scenario e.g. to a 50% substitution by 2030 and a 100% switch by 2050 (BCG, 2022).

Transportation

The transport sector in Norway has the following characteristics and perspectives for decarbonization:

- Being the second largest GHG emitting sector in Norway after industry, decarbonization of transport is key for Norway reaching its GHG targets included in its NDC and long-term strategy. Road transport is the largest emitter, therein (8.0 MtCO₂e in 2023), while navigation, fishing, aviation and other transport means in total almost reach road emissions (7.7 MtCO₂e in 2023, see Figure 12).
- Sea transport in Norway includes cruise ship lines like well-known Hurtigruten. Despite the perceived prominence, cruise ships are no major contributors to GHG emissions in Norway. Yet, Norwegian regulation in this sub-sector might trigger technological change in the marine sector beyond this branch (NZ, 2024).
- Electric vehicle (EV) market penetration has been strongly supported by governmental interventions, of which the key mechanisms are (IEA, 2022):

For fossil fuel cars

- High registration tax on purchase
- CO₂ tax
- Road use tax

For electric vehicles

- Substantial subsidies
- Remission of Value Added Tax
- One-off exemption from registration tax
- Reduced road tolls as well as ferry and parking fees.
- Due to the early and lasting governmental support schemes, Norway has become world leader in electric vehicle (EV) sales, having reached a share of zero emission vehicles and plug-in hybrid vehicles of 64.5% in 2021 (IEA, 2022) and 86% in 2022 (Climate Action Tracker, 2022).
- Regarding the car stock, too, Norway achieved a world leading share of zero-emission vehicles of 16% in 2021 with a sales share of 64.5% (i.e. excluding plug-in hybrid vehicles; IEA, 2022).

- In total, the transport sector shows a slightly declining GHG emission trend since 2015, driven by the uptake of electric vehicles in road transport (Figure 12). Electrification, biofuel blending and increased efficiency are the drivers of emission reduction (BCG, 2022).

Buildings

The building sector accounted for around one third of the total final energy consumption in Norway (IEA, 2022). It is highly electrified – Norway has one of the highest shares of heat pumps per household in the world (IEA 2022) – with bioenergy (wood) and district heat constituting the residual energy demand. Accordingly, the building sector is not a key contributor to Norway’s GHG emissions. Improving the energy efficiency of buildings, however, is still considered a low-hanging fruit by the NOU 2023 report. Like for the industry and energy supply sector, policy measures in Norway for the building sector relate to the political framework for buildings in the EU: Energy performance certificates are required when buildings are built, leased or sold (IEA, 2022). Very progressively, the government also banned the installation of fossil fuel-based heating systems since 2016 and the use of heating oil since 2020 (IEA, 2022). At present, no heating oil is consumed by the building sector any more, accordingly.

Energy supply system

The Norwegian energy supply system reveals a two-fold face: On the one hand, domestic electricity generation is widely defossilised, and the buildings and services sectors are highly electrified (Figure 7). Yet, fossil oil and gas extraction from Norway by far exceed the national demand, constituting a major source of the EU’s fossil fuel imports (Figure 8).

For further defossilizing the Norwegian demand sectors, the production of hydrogen from renewable sources is one focus of the Norwegian technology support schemes. For the production of such defossilised synthetic fuels as well as direct electrification of the demand sectors a strong and very ambitious expansion of renewable energy capacities and production as well as the necessary grid expansion is key for the energy sector (Figure 9).

Figure 7: Energy demand by energy carrier per sector, and electricity generation by source in 2020 (IEA, 2022)

Figure 8: Overview of energy production, supply and demand in Norway 2020 (IEA, 2022)
(TES: Total Energy Supply, TFC: Total Final Consumption)

Figure 9: Sample of forecasts of power consumption to 2050 from The Energy Commission (NOU, 2023)

Changing climatic conditions in Norway have structural implications for the Norwegian energy sector, being strongly based on hydropower use. The following effects on Norway’s energy demand and supply infrastructure are observed or expected in the future (IEA, 2022):

- The overall river runoff is expected to increase by the end of the century, yielding preferential conditions for Norway’s hydropower-based system in combination with its electrification strategy.

- In the same time, the necessity increases to compensate for higher seasonal water runoff gaps, caused by higher spring rainfalls, an earlier snowmelt and reduced summer runoff.
- On the demand side, the trend to milder winters will reduce energy demand for space heating. This effect is expected especially for the southern parts of Norway.
- Norway's infrastructure is expected to be increasingly exposed to storm surges and strong winds. Storms have been – together with snowfalls – the most common reason for electricity supply interruptions in the last years.

AFOLU (Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use)

39% of Norway's land surface is covered by forest, while, due to the climatic conditions of a country with its mainland north of 57-degree latitude, only 3 percent is farmland (Knutsen, 2020). Norway's forests constitute a considerable sink of almost -20 MtCO₂e/a at a total domestic emission level excluding LULUCF of +50 MtCO₂e/a (Figure 1). Forest cover has increased by around 12% between 2011 and 2020 regarding the growing wood stock. This tendency is expected to continue as a further increase towards 2025, according to Norway's national forestry accounting plan (Climate Action Tracker, 2022).

The Norwegian Governments long-term low-emission strategy for 2050 explicitly requires the sustainable management of forests and other land categories and national resources in a way that promotes removals of GHG and minimized GHG emission from this sector (NOU, 2023). Norway's Climate Action Plan outlines the following measures to further increase carbon removals by its forests (IEA, 2022):

- Additional tree planting
- Fertilisation
- Forest management methods.

Regarding peatlands as one focal part in Norway's LULUCF-related emissions and removals, considered strategic elements of emission reductions are (IEA, 2022):

- Reducing peatland degradation, including a ban on peat extraction
- Peatland restoration
- A land tax.

Norway's agriculture sector is characterized by its geographical and climatic preconditions as a far northern country: Grain yields per hectare are lower than in most European countries, and Norway is one of the few countries in Europe that cannot grow sugar crops (Knutsen, 2020). As a consequence, in many parts of Norway, fodder crops are the more or less only alternative of agricultural use of land, with grass being the most important group. Grass-based livestock production is thus "the backbone of Norwegian agriculture" as NIBIO states, one of Norway's largest research institutes (Figure 10, Knutsen, 2020). Both, the production and consumption of meat have steadily increased during the last 30-40 years, with increased poultry meat consumption being the main trend (Knutsen 2020).

In total, in the long-term perspective, GHG removals from LULUCF are expected to remain at current levels toward 2050 (Figure 1).

Figure 10: Production, import and export of major farm commodities in 2018 (Knutsen 2020)

Global conditions

The European energy crisis resulting from the Russian invasion in Ukraine in 2022 has strongly affected Norway's international energy economic position, even strengthening the role of fossils for Norway. How the global fossil fuel (net) phase-out transition practically develops will be a major driver of change of economic structures in Norway and will presumably have major influence on Norway's economic capabilities for domestic GHG mitigation efforts. Norway dual role – with current domestic national GHG emissions of around 50 MtCO₂/a by far exceeding GHG emissions of 500 MtCO₂ from exported fossils extracted by the Norwegian petroleum industry (Figure 13) – originates from the fundamental decision on UN level to account for GHG emission on a domestic, i.e. sovereign territory basis. A change of an accounting method from domestic consumption-oriented GHG emission accounting to a production of energy carriers-oriented accounting, however, is hardly imaginable. It shall be observed whether the Norwegian way to resolve its ambiguous position reveals show case mechanisms for countries and regions in similar situations, worldwide. The role which CCS will practically play for net-zero GHG ambitions of Norway and for the role of fossil fuel exports in the Norwegian economy could be key aspect, therein.

Key messages for next NDC

Improvements since 2015

Nine years ago, on July 2015, the Climate Action Tracker considered the overall climate mitigation ambition of Norway as medium. The same rating applied to the Norwegian stated Intended National Determined Contributions (INDC) of -40% of that year, however, being closer to "inadequate" than to "sufficient" (Climate Action Tracker, 2015). Norway's updated 2030 NDC emission reduction target of -55% is a clear improvement in this regard, however, lifting the level of required policy action and finance even higher. As Figure 1 shows Norway could only achieve marginal GHG emission reductions from 1990 to 2020, with a steady, yet comparatively small downward trend only observed from around 2015 on.

Failures and lessons learned

Despite the established policies addressing the demand sectors and the domestic energy provision, gross carbon emissions have stayed more or less unchanged since 1990. The reasons for the reduction of net emissions compared 1990 are found in LULUCF sinks. Figure 1 indicates that the -55% NDC target will not be achieved based on what is projected until 2035. An unprecedented raise of the effective rate of emission reduction, i.e. accelerated implementation of effective policies and measures beyond LULUCF needs to be reached. The 2023 NOU report of the Climate Change Committee concludes, among a broad spectrum of specific approaches and options recommended, that the implementation of the Norwegian climate policy must be more credible, broad and comprehensive, must not be postponed, and needs a stronger link with societal development in general in Norway.

Key messages for the next NDC

According to the Climate Actions Tracker 2022, the 2030 NDC target of -55% corresponds to the minimum ambition in Norway for achieving a below 1.5°C world. Raising the quantitative NDC target for 2030 on a higher level would thus not be an undisputed claim and key message to the next NDC. Preparing for looking beyond 2030 already in the NDCs, is crucial, however. As a preparatory measure, the Climate Change Committee recommends a study on when it is realistic to achieve net zero for the different sectoral emitters. Explicit **emission reduction targets for 2040** could be stated on this basis like an emission free Norwegian road transport sector in 2040 (see NOU, 2023), following the recent EU practice for setting climate targets for 2040 and a pathway for GHG emission reductions over 2025-2050. This would help to monitor the bridging of the twenty-year gap between 2030 and 2050, while yet only being a little more than five years ahead of 2030. However, many studies emphasize the importance of raising the ambition and impact of the **Norwegian policy measures** to reach the 2030 NDC target, with the 2050 Climate Change Committee report and its recommendations being in the front row (NOU, 2023). Concretely defining these policy measures, being validated by improved models and tools for the corresponding quantified system pathways (NOU, 2023), and anchoring them explicitly in the next NDC policies statement would be a credible way of backing the Norwegian NDC target with concrete measures.

Regarding exported **fossil oil and gas from Norway**, the trajectory of the connected GHG emissions is one important determinant in reaching the EU's emission reduction target of -90% for 2040 and net zero in 2050. By the Paris Agreements mechanisms, emission reduction targets stated in the countries' NDCs have implications for the Norwegian oil and gas extraction and export. Committing to a well below 2° world thus implies to have explicit, credible and accepted pathways to decarbonizing this important share of the Norwegian national product.

Annex

Key socio-economic figures and outlook

	Unit	2022	2024	2030	2050
Population	[million]	5.43	5.55	5.75	6.15

Table 1: Norway – Population and GDP (Statistisk sentralbyrå 2024)

Population in Norway is anticipated to constantly grow until 2050 by the National population projections (Statistisk sentralbyrå, 2024). The main projection, among a low and high projection, of the national forecast is depicted in Table 1.

Trajectories of GDP per capita until 2060 from the Norwegian Ministry of Finance are shown in Figure 11 for different levels of productivity grows, with the grey line being the 2021 white paper baseline (Ministry of Finance, 2021). From 2020 to 2050, GDP per capita is expected to grow by about 50% in the 2021 baseline projection. In absolute terms, Norwegian GDP in 2021 amounted to 3700 billion NOK including oil and gas extraction, transport via pipelines and ocean transport (National Communication, 2023), corresponding to 414 billion USD based on purchasing power parity (OECD PPP, 2024).

(Please note that population growth in Table 1 and GDP per capita projections in Figure 11 are from different sources and are not necessarily based on the same assumption about population growth.)

Figure 11: Mainland Norway GDP per capita, Index 1970=100 (Ministry of Finance 2021)

Current emission situation

The total GHG emissions in Norway amount to around 50 MtCO₂e/a (BCG, 2022), excluding land use, land use change and forestry (LULUCF). This translated into Norwegian per capita emissions of slightly above 9 t per year. Land use and forestry constitute a considerable sink in the order of magnitude of -15 MtCO₂e/a (Figure 1). About half of the Norwegian GHG emissions are covered by the European Emission Trading System ETS-1. The vast majority of ETS emissions originate from industrial plants and the petroleum industry and a minor share from aviation and energy provision.

Figure 12: Greenhouse gas emissions by sector in Norway (NOU, 2023)

In comparison of the sectors, the industry sector induced the highest GHG emissions. The domestic emissions from the oil and gas extraction industry exceeded emissions from the other manufacturing industries and mining in Norway in 2020 (Figure 12). The second highest emissions originate from the transport sector. Road traffic in Norway alone therein exceeds emissions from aviation, navigation, fishing and other transport activities, as far as accounted for in the domestic balance. With the electricity sector being almost completely based on renewable energy sources and the building being highly electrified with heat pumps (Figure 7), the GHG emissions from agriculture in Norway exceed those of all the remaining sectors.

When looking at emissions induced from the combustion of the fossil oil and gas extracted by the Norwegian petroleum industry and exported from Norway, Figure 13 shows that these by exceed domestic emissions by a factor of around 10 at the beginning of this decade.

Figure 13: Annual CO₂ emissions from combustion of produced Norwegian oil and gas (NOU, 2023)

Based on the Norwegian Petroleum Directorate's forecasts for 2021-2025, Source: Robbie Andrew, CICERO

Pathways for Norway – Data tables

	1990 (mill. tonnes of CO ₂ e)	Percentage of total (1990)	2021 (mill. tonnes of CO ₂ e)	Percentage of total (2021)	2050 (mill. tonnes of CO ₂ e)	Percentage of total (2050)
Oil and gas production	8,2	16	12,2	25	0,9	18
Manufacturing industries and mining	19,2	38	11,7	24	-0,5	-9
Energy supply	0,3	1	1,7	4	-0,4	-8
Heating in other industries and households	2,8	5	0,6	1	0,2	5
Road traffic	7,4	14	8,7	18	0,0	0
Aviation, navigation, fishing, motorised equip. etc.	5,3	10	7,5	15	0,1	2
Agriculture	4,9	10	4,7	10	3,8	76
Other	3,1	6	2,2	4	0,8	17
Total	51,3	100	49,2	100	5,0	100

Source: The 2050 Climate Change Committee

Table 2: Sectoral contributions to the 2050 GHG target from the technical analysis (NOU, 2023)

Emissions and removals from forestry and land use are not included.

Graphical figure for the sectoral data of Table 2:

Figure 14: Sectoral contributions to the 2050 GHG target from the technical analysis (NOU, 2023)

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Corresponding Author

Dipl.-Systemwiss. Stefan Kronshage
stefan.kronshage@dlr.de

PARTICIPANTS

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